

ECONOMIC EVALUATION OF LOAN BORROWED BY FARMERS IN BULDHANA DISTRICT

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Abstract

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy, supporting a large population directly involved in farming and allied sectors. In India, agricultural credit is essential for supporting farming activities and ensuring sustainable development. In Buldhana district, Maharashtra's Western Vidarbha zone, agriculture is the primary livelihood. The region faces challenges like rain-fed farming, rising input costs, and market fluctuations, making access to agricultural loans essential. Seasonal farming and unpredictable rainfall drive the need for financial support to buy inputs, improve irrigation, and manage debt. Timely and affordable credit is crucial for sustaining and growing the agricultural sector in Buldhana.

This study examines the socio-economic profile, cropping patterns, loan-taking behaviours, and repayment schedules of loan-borrowing farmers in Buldhana district, Maharashtra. Data were collected from 60 farmers, analyzing variables like age, family size, education, landholding, annual income, and the types of loans taken. The majority of loan borrowers are middle-aged (31-60 years), have medium-sized families (4-6 members), and have a basic education (up to 12th grade). Agriculture is the primary occupation for 80% of the respondents, with 55% holding small landholdings (2.5 to 5 acres). Soybean and cotton are the most widely grown Kharif crops, while gram and wheat are the main Rabi crops. Cropping intensity is 146.49%. Most loans taken were for agricultural purposes, specifically crop loans (88.33%). Repayment behaviour shows a high rate of default, with 58.33% of farmers failing to repay their loans, largely due to expectations of government debt waivers and low agricultural income. Partial repayment was often attributed to family expenses and health issues.

The study highlights the challenges faced by farmers in terms of unstable income, high production costs, and debt repayment issues, emphasizing the need for better support systems and financial literacy programs. This research offers a comprehensive view of the financial and agricultural realities of farmers in Buldhana district, providing insights into their borrowing practices and repayment challenges.

Keywords: Loan, Repayment, Economic evaluation.

Introduction

Agriculture is the backbone of the Indian economy, supporting a large population directly involved in farming and allied sectors. It contributes around 16-18% to India's GDP and plays a crucial role in exports with products like rice, cotton, and spices. Despite its significance, Indian agriculture faces numerous challenges such as small landholdings, reliance on rain-fed farming, climate unpredictability, rising input costs, and limited access to modern practices. These challenges impact farmers' productivity and livelihoods.

In India, agricultural credit is essential for supporting farming activities and ensuring sustainable development. The credit system consists of both informal and formal sources. Informal sources include friends, moneylenders, and traders, often leading to debt traps due to high-interest rates. Formal institutions such as commercial banks, cooperatives, and microfinance institutions provide more structured credit solutions. Institutional credit plays a key role in enhancing agricultural productivity and ensuring rural development, particularly for small and marginal farmers who face financial constraints.

The government has introduced several schemes to provide agricultural loans, such as the Kisan Credit Card (KCC) and Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY), to help farmers access credit and manage crop losses. However, challenges remain, including delays in loan disbursement, high-interest rates, and inadequate loan amounts. Reforms like digitalization and infrastructure expansion in rural areas are needed to improve the credit system's effectiveness.

In Buldhana district, located in Maharashtra's Western Vidarbha zone, agriculture is the primary source of livelihood. The region faces challenges like rain-fed farming, rising input costs, and market fluctuations, making access to agricultural loans crucial for farmers. Seasonal farming and unpredictable rainfall create the need for financial support to purchase inputs, develop irrigation facilities, and repay debts. Addressing these challenges with timely and affordable credit is key to ensuring the sustainability and growth of the agricultural sector in Buldhana.

Objective

1. To study socio-economic status of selected farmers in Buldhana district.
2. To access the loan borrowed by farmers for agriculture and non-agriculture purpose.
3. To evaluate the repayment schedule adopted by farmers in Buldhana district.

3. Materials and Methods**Area of Study**

The study was conducted in Buldhana district, selecting two tehsils: Buldhana and Khamgaon. Three villages were chosen from each tehsil, namely Warwand, Sao, and Dahid Budruk from Buldhana tehsil, and Nandri, Botha, and Mandani from Khamgaon tehsil. A total of 60 farmers, who had taken loans from banking institutions, were randomly selected for the study.

Sample Size

The study involved 60 farmers to ensure reliable results, minimizing margin of error and increasing confidence in the findings.

Sampling Method

Farmers were selected using a random sampling method with equal distance for data collection.

Research Instrument

A data collection schedule was prepared in consultation with the institute guide to record information from the selected farmers.

Period of Study

The data was collected for the financial year 2023-24.

Source of Data

Primary data was collected from farmers through questionnaires and interviews, while secondary data was sourced from government reports, academic journals, and books.

Analytical Tools

Socio-economic variables such as family size, income, education, age, sex, and landholding were analyzed through simple tabular analysis. Data was categorized based on the purpose of loans (agricultural and non-agricultural) and repayment schedules were compared with standard financing plans.

Result And Discussion

Socio-economic status of selected farmers in Buldhana district.

Age, Family members, Education level of loan borrower's farmers in Buldhana district

Table No.1 Age, Family members, Education level of loan borrower's farmers in Buldhana district

Sr. No	Variables	Category	No of Farmers	Percent Share
1	Age	Below 20	0	0.00
		21-30	9	15.00
		31-40	14	23.33
		41-50	10	16.67
		51-60	16	26.67
		61 and above	11	18.33
2	Family	Small (Up to 3)	20	33.33
		Medium (4-6)	32	53.33
		Large (Above 6)	8	13.33
3	Education	Illiterate	5	8.33
		1-7 Standards	20	33.33
		8-12 Standards	22	36.67
		Graduate Level	13	21.67
4	Sex	Male	60	100.00
		Female	0	0.00
5	Caste	OBC	39	65.00
		SC/ST	20	33.33
		VJNT	1	1.67

The study revealed that among the 60 farmers, the majority (26.67%) were aged 51-60, while 23.33% were between 31-40 years. Most families were medium-sized (53.33%), followed by small (33.33%), and large families (13.33%). Regarding education, 36.67% of the

farmers had studied up to 8-12 standards, while 33.33% had completed 1-7 standards, and 21.67% were graduates. All participants were male, and the majority belonged to the OBC category (65%), with SC/ST farmers making up 33.33%, and VJNT farmers 1.67%.

Farming experience, Occupation, Social participation, and Land holding of loan borrowers farmers in Buldhana district**Table No.2: Farming experience, Occupation, Social participation, and Land holding of loan borrowers farmers in Buldhana district**

Sr. No	Variables	Category	No of Farmers	Percent Share
1	Farming Experience	01-20	33	55
		21-40	22	36.67
		41-60	5	8.33
2	Occupation	Agriculture	48	80
		Agriculture and Service	6	10
		Agriculture and Business	6	10
3	Social Participation	Regularly	44	73.33
		Occasionally	13	21.67
		No Participation	3	5
4	Land Holding	Marginal(Up to 2.5 Acre)	10	16.67
		Small(2.5 to 5 Acre)	33	55
		Medium(5 to 10 Acre)	16	26.67
		Large(10 to 25 Acre)	1	1.67

The data shows that 55% of the farmers had 1-20 years of farming experience, while 36.67% had 21-40 years. Most farmers (80%) were solely involved in agriculture, with 10% combining agriculture with either service or business. In terms of social participation, 73.33% were regularly involved, while 21.67% participated occasionally. Regarding

land holdings, 55% were small-scale farmers with 2.5 to 5 acres, 26.67% had medium holdings (5-10 acres), and 16.67% were marginal farmers with up to 2.5 acres, while only 1.67% had large holdings (10-25 acres).

Table No. 3 Annual income of loan borrowers' farmers in Buldhana district

Sr No	Category (Rs)	No of Farmers	Per cent Share	Average Income
1	0-30000	4	6.67	29250
2	30001-60000	32	53.33	45062.5
3	60001-90000	6	10.00	77500
4	90001-120000	10	16.67	104000
5	120001-150000	8	13.33	145625
Total		60	100	

In Buldhana district, 53.33% of the farmers had an annual income between Rs. 30,001 and 60,000, with an average income of Rs. 45,062.5. Around 16.67% earned between Rs. 90,001 and 1,20,000, while 13.33% had incomes between Rs. 1,20,001 and 1,50,000. A

smaller portion, 10%, earned Rs. 60,001 to 90,000, and only 6.67% had incomes below Rs. 30,000. The average income among all categories varied, reflecting diverse economic conditions.

Cropping Pattern of Loan borrowers Farmers in Buldhana district**Table No. 4: Cropping Pattern of Loan borrowers Farmers in Buldhana district**

Sr.No	Crops Sown	Area Sown (In Acres)	No of Farmers	Average Sown Land	Per cent Share
	Kharif				
1	Cotton	107	30	1.78	26.37
2	Soybean	144.9	32	2.42	35.85
3	Tur	20.25	13	0.34	5.04
	Rabi				
5	Gram	79	22	1.32	19.56
6	Wheat	41.4	10	0.69	10.22
	Summer				
7	Onion	11	5	0.18	2.67
8	Gavar	1	1	0.02	0.30
Total		404.55	113	6.75	100.00
Cropping intensity of Loan borrowers Farmers in Buldhana District					
9	Gross Area Sown	404.55			
	Net Area Sown	276.15			
	Cropping intensity (per cent)				146.49

In Buldhana district, loan-borrowing farmers primarily cultivated soybean and cotton during the Kharif season, with soybean covering 35.85% of the sown area and cotton covering 26.37%. Tur was grown on 5.04% of the area. For Rabi crops, gram and wheat were the main crops, covering 19.56% and 10.22% of the land, respectively. During

Categorization of Loan taken by Farmers**Table No. 5: Categorization of Loan taken by Farmers**

Sr. No	Categories of Loan Borrowers	Loan Amount	No of Farmers	Average Loan	Per cent share
A	Agriculture purpose				
1	Crop Loan Farmers	4338000	53	81849.06	88.33
2	Business Loan (ACABC) Farmers	400000	1	400000	1.67
3	Mudra Loan (Allied agri)	50000	1	50000	1.67
B	Non-agriculture purpose				
4	Education Loan Farmers	400000	1	400000	1.67
5	Home Loan Farmers	400000	2	200000	3.33
6	Personal Loan Farmers	250000	2	125000	3.33
	Total	5838000	60		100

In Buldhana district, 88.33% of farmers took loans for agricultural purposes, with crop loans being the most common, averaging ₹81,849.06 per farmer. Business loans under the ACABC scheme and Mudra loans for allied agriculture made up 1.67% each. For non-agricultural purposes, education and home loans were taken by a small

the summer, onion and gavar were cultivated on smaller portions of land. The total gross area sown was 404.55 acres, with a net area sown of 276.15 acres, resulting in a cropping intensity of 146.49%.

The loan borrowed by farmers for agriculture and non-agriculture purpose.

number of farmers, accounting for 1.67% and 3.33%, respectively. Personal loans also comprised 3.33% of the total. Overall, the total loan amount across all categories was ₹5,838,000.

Repayment schedule adopted by loan borrowers in Buldhana district**Table No. 6: Repayment schedule adopted by loan borrowers in Buldhana district**

Sr.No	Loan Scheme	No of Farmers	Regular Repayment	Per cent Share
1	Central Kisan Credit Card	53	23	76.67
2	Home Loan Scheme	2	2	6.67
3	Personal Loan	2	2	6.67
4	Education Loan Scheme	1	1	3.33
5	Pradhan Mandri Mudra Yojana Allied Agri	1	1	3.33
6	ACABC(Agri Clinic And Agri Business Scheme)	1	1	3.33
	Total	60	30	100

Defaulters of Central Kisan Credit Card Scheme are 35 Farmers Which is 58.33% of total Borrowers.

In Buldhana district, out of 60 loan borrowers, 50% made regular repayments. The Central Kisan Credit Card (KCC) scheme had the highest participation, with 76.67% of farmers, but 58.33% of these

farmers defaulted. Home, personal, education, and Mudra loans had a 100% repayment rate for the small number of borrowers, while the ACABC scheme also saw full repayment

Comparison Between Loan Borrowers and Regular Repayee

4.3.1: Repayment behaviour of loan borrowers farmers in Buldhana district

Table No. 7: Repayment behaviour of loan borrowers farmers in Buldhana district

Sr. No	Variables	Categories	No of Farmers	Percent Share
1	Extent of Repayment	Fully Repaid	6	6.67
		Partly Repaid	21	35
		Fully Not Repaid	33	58.33
		Total	60	100
2	Reasons For The Full Repayment	To Take Another Loan	5	50
		To Maintain Credibility	5	50
		Proper Supervision by the Bank	4	100
		Total	4	100
3	Reasons For The Partial Repayment of Loan	Insufficient Income	3	14.28
		Crop Failures	1	4.76
		Family Problems and Expenses on Health And Education of Children	17	80.95
		Total	21	100
4	Reasons For the Fully Not Repayment of Loan	Expecting Debt Waiver and Debt Reliefs by Government	36	60
		Less of Agricultural Income	9	14.28
		Low Price for or Agricultural Produce	9	25.71
		Total	35	100

loans for non-agricultural purposes, such as education and personal loans.

The repayment behavior highlights a significant issue, as only 6.67% of farmers fully repaid their loans, while 58.33% did not repay at all. Expectation of debt waivers and low agricultural income were the primary reasons for non-repayment, reflecting the vulnerability of farmers to economic instability. Proper supervision by banks and a desire to take another loan were the primary motivations for full repayment. Family problems and insufficient income were key reasons for partial repayment.

Overall, the data suggests that while farmers in Buldhana district are highly dependent on loans for agriculture, their repayment capabilities are limited due to economic challenges such as low agricultural income and the expectation of government debt relief.

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The repayment behavior of loan borrowers in Buldhana district shows that 58.33% of farmers did not fully repay their loans, while 35% partly repaid, and only 6.67% fully repaid. Of those who fully repaid, 50% did so to obtain another loan and 50% due to proper bank supervision. Among those who made partial payments, 80.95% cited family problems and education expenses as the primary reason. For those who did not repay, 60% were expecting government debt waivers, with 25.71% citing low agricultural income and 14.28% pointing to insufficient income.

Conclusion

The study of loan borrowers in Buldhana district reveals several significant socio-economic and behavioral patterns. The majority of farmers (41-60 years of age) come from medium-sized families (4-6 members), and their education levels are primarily between 1-12 standards. Almost all borrowers are male (100%), with a large portion belonging to the OBC category (65%).

In terms of farming experience, over half (55%) have 1-20 years of experience, with agriculture being the primary occupation for 80% of the farmers. Social participation is relatively strong, with 73.33% regularly engaged in social activities.

Regarding financial status, more than half of the farmers (53.33%) fall within an income range of Rs. 30,001-60,000, while a smaller portion (16.67%) earns between Rs. 90,001-120,000 annually. The cropping pattern shows that soybean and cotton are the most commonly sown crops, followed by gram and wheat. Cropping intensity is relatively high at 146.49%.

When it comes to loan categorization, 88.33% of loans were taken for agricultural purposes, primarily crop loans. Only a small portion took

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